

CAN Bus System, VeCure and IDS

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Abstract. Many years ago, vehicles had many lines, and some actions were harder or we had many problems with them, such as diagnosis, installation, replacing equipment, etc. Also, they were in danger. Thanks to these problems, engineers introduced the CAN Bus system to the world. This system decreased line number and length, and they are faster. It isn't really safe for communications, but it is recommended for platforms that don't have any listeners in Network. In this age, airplanes, cars, ships and etc are using this system. In this paper we will review CAN Bus, and its problems and some ideas and some solved solution for that.

Keywords: CAN Bus System · Controller Area Network · IDS · VeCure

1 Introduction

Controller Area Network is a useful protocol for vehicles, ships, airplanes, electronic equipment, etc. They're not safe for platforms which they're have many listener in a network. So engineers have made some platforms for them.

2 CAN Bus data transmission

Regarding to Wikipedia definition of CAN Bus system, CAN data transmission uses a lossless bitwise arbitration method of contention resolution. This arbitration method requires all nodes on the CAN network to be synchronized to sample every bit on the CAN network at the same time. This is why some call CAN synchronous. Unfortunately the term synchronous is imprecise since the data is transmitted in an asynchronous format, namely without a clock signal.

The CAN specifications use the terms dominant bits and recessive bits, where dominant is a logical 0 (actively driven to a voltage by the transmitter) and recessive is a logical 1 (passively returned to a voltage by a resistor). The idle state is represented by the recessive level (Logical 1). If one node transmits a dominant bit and another node transmits a recessive bit then there is a collision and the dominant bit wins. This means there is no delay to the higher-priority message, and the node transmitting the lower-priority message automatically attempts to re-transmit six-bit clocks after the end of the dominant message. This makes CAN very suitable as a real-time prioritized communications system.

The exact voltages for a logical 0 or 1 depend on the physical layer used, but the basic principle of CAN requires that each node listen to the data on the

CAN network including the transmitting node(s) itself (themselves). If a logical 1 is transmitted by all transmitting nodes at the same time, then a logical 1 is seen by all of the nodes, including both the transmitting node(s) and receiving node(s). If a logical 0 is transmitted by all transmitting node(s) at the same time, then a logical 0 is seen by all nodes. If a logical 0 is being transmitted by one or more nodes, and a logical 1 is being transmitted by one or more nodes, then a logical 0 is seen by all nodes including the node(s) transmitting the logical 1. When a node transmits a logical 1 but sees a logical 0, it realizes that there is a contention and it quits transmitting. By using this process, any node that transmits a logical 1, when another node transmits a logical 0, loses the arbitration and drops out. A node that loses arbitration re-queues its message for later transmission and the CAN frame bit-stream continues without error until only one node is left transmitting. This means that the node that transmits the first 1 loses arbitration. Since the 11 (or 29 for CAN 2.0B) bit identifier is transmitted by all nodes at the start of the CAN frame, the node with the lowest identifier transmits more zeros at the start of the frame, and that is the node that wins the arbitration or has the highest priority.

For example, consider an 11-bit ID CAN network, with two nodes with IDs of 15 (binary representation, 00000001111) and 16 (binary representation, 00000010000). If these two nodes transmit at the same time, each will first transmit the start bit then transmit the first six zeros of their ID with no arbitration decision being made.

When ID bit 4 is transmitted, the node with the ID of 16 transmits a 1 (recessive) for its ID, and the node with the ID of 15 transmits a 0 (dominant) for its ID. When this happens, the node with the ID of 16 knows it transmitted a 1, but sees a 0 and realizes that there is a collision and it lost arbitration. Node 16 stops transmitting which allows the node with ID of 15 to continue its transmission without any loss of data. The node with the lowest ID will always win the arbitration and therefore has the highest priority.

Bit rates up to 1 Mbit/s are possible at network lengths below 40 m. Decreasing the bit rate allows longer network distances (e.g. 500 m at 125 kbit/s). The improved CAN FD standard allows increasing the bit rate after arbitration and can increase the speed of the data section by a factor of up to ten or more of the arbitration bit rate.

3 CAN Bus in Electric cars

According to the communication structure of CAN BUS network on EV, Design method of CAN BUS network communication structure for electric vehicle paper[1] works out a SAE J1939 application layer protocol meet the system functional requirements, and designs the software and hardware for the system. First, design the CAN BUS work nod for EV, including the master node, the light node, air conditioning node, doors and instrument node, etc, and the draw the CAN BUS topology diagram. Meanwhile, according to the concrete situation of EV, work out an application layer protocol that consistent with the SAE

J1939 protocol, and the information allocation table and message structure chart of CAN BUS network node is also presented. Secondly, design the hardware and software for the CAN BUS communication network. Hardware interface circuit mainly consist of CAN communication controller SJA1000, high-speed opt coupler 6N137 and CAN BUS driver 82C250, and design schematic circuit diagram for CAN bus system hardware. The software designs for CAN BUS network are mainly the design of CAN BUS data communication and exchange between nodes, and communication processing for switch-signal, analog signal. The design of software communication module includes CAN initialization unit, message sending unit, message receiving unit and the interrupt service unit. Finally, the CAN BUS network communication system the paper designed is applied to the new energy bus produced by CENS Energy-Tech Co., Ltd. which is dedicated in the Shanghai World Expo. From the battery voltage data collected when EV are running, we can see that the system is accurate, stable without number lost, frame dropping and transfer error in data communication. The design has practical value promoting the application of new energy vehicles.

Fig. 1. CAN Bus in Vehicles

4 Controller Area Network and IDS

Controller area network (CAN) bus has become the most used protocol in automotive network since its robustness and efficiency. However, CAN bus does not have enough security properties to protect the whole automotive system even to protect its network. So, security mechanism to protect CAN bus became an emergency need. One of the efficient methods for securing CAN bus, is Intrusion Detection System (IDS). In this work, a simple intrusion detection method for CAN bus is proposed. Our algorithm does not require any modification in standard procedure of CAN bus nor to be implemented in each calculators of network. [2]

5 VeCure

Vehicles are being revolutionized by integrating modern computing and communication technologies in order to improve both user experience and driving safety. As a result, vehicular systems that used to be closed systems are opening up various interfaces, such as Bluetooth, 3G/4G, GPS, etc., to the outside world, thus introducing new opportunities for cyber attacks. It has been recently demonstrated that modern vehicles are vulnerable to several remote attacks launched through Bluetooth and cellular interfaces, allowing the attacker to take full control of the vehicle. The common root cause of these attacks is the lack of message authentication for the vehicle's internal bus system, called Controller Area Network (CAN). In this work, we propose VeCure - a practical security framework for vehicular systems, which can fundamentally solve the message authentication issue of the CAN bus. VeCure is designed to be compatible with existing vehicle system architectures, and employs a trust group structure and a novel message authentication scheme with offline computation capability to minimize online message processing delay and deployment cost. We built a proof-of-concept prototype on a testbed using Freescale's automotive development boards. The experimental results show that VeCure only introduces 50us additional delay to process a message, which is at least 20-fold faster than any existing solution. [3]

6 Conclusion

We have reviewed some ideas and techniques in this paper with details. Also we understood that CAN Bus system isn't a safe protocol but we have some faster and safer ways. These things are used in airplanes, ships, vehicles, televisions, computers, cell phones, etc.

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